

Comparative Study on Geopolymer Coated Recycled Aggregate Concrete

Subrata Mandal^a, Somnath Ghosh^b

^aPrincipal, Haldia Institute of Technology, West Bengal, India

^b Emeritus Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Haldia Institute of Technology, West Bengal,
E-mail: principal.hit@hithaldia.in; sngcehit@gmail.com

Abstract

The interrelation of humans with their environment is extremely important. Human pressure on environment is a major issue. Fundamental debate on economic growth is focused in this paper. Historical role of technology is highlighted. The interrelation between technology and environment, are indicated. Though a fundamental shift of technology is indispensable but technology is not only a key to solve the environmental problems. Again, Green or Sustainable technology deals with the short-term and long-term impact on the environment. Recycling, renewable resources, health and safety issues, energy efficiency etc., are the most important aspects. It is environmentally friendly. No harmful emission to the air. Less operational cost. Never run out because of its renewable technology. It helps to reduce carbon dioxide emission in the air. It reduces global warming. This technology is a most important enabler of sustainability. It is accelerating net zero transitions to building more sustainable value chains. Some other important aspects of green technology are also highlighted in this paper.

Keywords: Green technology, Sustainability, Ecology, Growth, Debate, Renewable energy technology

1. Introduction

Initially, the term Sustainability referred to preservation of the forest, harvesting. The durability of global human progress was highlighted in a 1972 report. Future viability is broadly associated with the concept of sustainability. Humanity has given best effort to increase its economic activities, increases resource consumption and waste production. Due to these natural environment have surpassed the sustainable level. It threatens the natural environment which is most important to humans. Human needs has become an unreachable goal. Global political agenda, aligning the preservation of a functional natural environment with UN.

Interrelation of humans with their natural environment is an important issue. Introduction of the laws and dynamics, is necessary. Compounded human influences, the determinants of environmental pressure are introduced. The central topic of any discussion on sustainability issues is the growth debate. The concept of technology and technological development need to be discussed in a holistic manner. Dynamics of Technology are discussed indicating the interrelation of technology with environmental issues.

The creation of new technologies that foster research and stimulate innovation is the needs of hours. This technology is environmentally friendly. It includes issues with energy efficiency, health, and safety. Explore options like recycling and renewable resources. The use of renewable energy sources such as geothermal wells, solar panels, wind turbines, and dams must be explored. Alternative energy, stop exploiting fossil fuels, reduces greenhouse gases and slow down global warming. Tidal energy, vertical farming and self-sufficient buildings, have not received proper attention in the past. Attention is needed for natural waste management systems. This technology protects resources and limits the harm caused by

human activity. Sustainable development is the keystone of environmental technology. As a

result, it is required to consider social, economic, and environmental factors. It is an umbrella term that reduces human impacts on the natural environment.

Scientific research, including energy, agriculture, material science, and hydrology, atmospheric science, are needed to be nurtured. Objective of Green Technology is to reduce the environmental footprint of human activities, should be economically viable and profitable and provides better quality of life in harmony with nature. Products, processes, and systems are extremely important aspects. Proper design is essential to maximize mass, energy, space, and time efficiency.

Low-carbon public transport systems and infrastructure for fuel efficient is essential. Investments will be enhanced on clean energy, energy efficient buildings and equipment etc.. This will be the main pathway of economic development and growth.

The Internet, telephones, cars, planes, children's toys, and other gadgets are examples of technology. These types of equipment have impacted society greatly. They have made the movement of goods and people easier and faster. The Internet and cellphones have eased the way people communicate and pass information. In the modern world, it's impossible to live without technology. Technology has now become part of life.

Scaling up renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro, tidal, and geothermal energy is necessary. Additionally, green material processing technologies such as recycling, industrial symbiosis, and industrial ecology must be developed. Society's transportation system must be de-carbonized. The world's unsustainable systems need to be massively replaced with environmentally friendly, resilient systems that can be scaled up to address environmental degradation. To build a resilient society, it is necessary to anticipate difficulties and risks of global catastrophe and to prepare for them. Malnutrition is an extremely important problem and need proper attention in the future. Numerous factors are contributing to it, including widespread socioeconomic, environmental, and health problems, the phenomena of climate change, the depletion of natural resources, atmospheric pollution, outbreaks of vector-borne diseases, flooding, crop failures, etc.

These effects are mostly in developing countries, whose contributions to GHG emissions are far lower than rest of the industrialized world. Effective initiatives and strategies related to renewable power from waste, mitigation to climate change, creating job opportunities, and promotion of growth in GDP through wealth generation mechanisms. The 5R's (reduce, reuse, recycle, recover, and repair) approach to waste management is crucial. It includes things like protecting against soil erosion, gully issues, deforestation, and maintenance of the environment.

Developing wealth for farmers, the need to preserve biodiversity, a reduction in the demand for landfill waste disposal, the eradication of poverty, etc. Food security in the nation can be improved by increasing the production of organic fertilizer, promoting indigenous sustainable development technologies, and reducing the release of gases such as carbon dioxide and methane into the atmosphere. These actions also help the nation save foreign exchange.

1. Sustainability

The report *The Limits to Growth* indicated environment-based collapse (Meadows et al.,

1972). Population, food production, industrial production, pollution, and the use of non-renewable natural resources are all examples of economic sub-systems. A shift in the

fundamental pattern to avoid collapse within 100 years is essential. Dynamics of interrelated economic subsystems, *The Limits to Growth* is a pioneering scientific work.

After 15 years, the Brundtland Report (WCED-1987) defined sustainable development as meeting current demands without compromising the capacity of future generations to satisfy their own requirements. It included aligning societal (social and economic) development with ecological restrictions. Sustainable development has become the super ordinate notion. In the UN, Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015), economic growth and environmental quality is more reflected

2. Environment and Economy

The economy is a subsystem of earth ecosystem. It is a thermodynamically closed system. Humans depend on natural resources. Natural resources can be divided into two categories: flow resources and stock resources.

The combustion of fossil fuels is inherently dissipative. On the other hand, minerals that are used to make a product can be recycled. Once more, the environment acts as a waste sink since residues from economic activity are released into it. Due to the effects on an ecosystem's ability to function, the role of wastes is crucial.

Amenity services are provided by the environment. Even in the absence of any useful activity, the existence of a beautiful landscape provides value for humans. The environment performs fundamental aspects of life support. The natural greenhouse effect creates conditions that are favorable for the emergence and preservation of human life.

The challenge of the de-carbonizing industry is an economic challenge. Industry like, cement, steel, ammonia, and ethylene, which are of major carbon emissions as well as produces commodity products beside cost is a decisive consideration in purchasing decisions, a real challenge of de-carbonizing.

Currently willingness to pay more for sustainable products. The companies that de-carbonize will face economic disadvantage. Renewable energy sector is facing this problem from public perception point of view. Public willingness is not the only problem but financial support, the energy transition for industry and utilities towards renewable electricity is a real challenge, needs Govt. intervention. Collaborative approach may be adopted.

3. Environmental Science

It is essential to be aware of the environment/economy relationship. Understanding and evaluation of human activity with respect to environmental issues, is extremely important. Therefore, some fundamental concepts and principles of environmental science is relevant.

Ecology concepts need to comprehend the effects of human activities and the nature of the environment. Accordingly policies are to be framed and implemented.

4. Thermodynamics

The laws of thermodynamics are incontrovertible. Thermodynamics to economics was

compared. Again, Thermodynamics is concerned with energy characteristic. This gradient is

extremely important to perform work or supply heat. The first law of thermodynamics stipulates that “energy can neither be created nor destroyed”. While it changes forms during

transformations between different types of energy and the total quantity in an isolated system is conserved. Energy is neither created nor consumed in an economic sense in society. An application of the first law, the materials-balance principle, is extremely important. The Entropy law is considered to be the root cause of economic scarcity. Entropy itself is a measure of dispersed energy. There is a set limit to the efficiency of a system. Complete material recycling is practically impossible. Thermodynamics laws help for a better understanding of the important issues for sustainability.

1. Using the available energy resources efficiently is essential for economic activities.
2. Physical resources of low entropy are extremely important for managing processes.
3. The proportionate use of resources involves the release of waste into the environment. However, prospects for recycling and a circular economy, need to be understood in depth.
4. The applicability to complex socio-economic systems is constrained by the generic nature of thermodynamics. The disposal of residuals have many implications for the environmental point of view. Entropy to economic aspects should be treated with carefully.

5. Ecology

An ecosystem is a dynamic system of interconnected plants, animals, microorganisms, and physical environmental components. The advantages that humans derive from ecosystems are known as ecosystem services. Consequently, dynamic and complex systems are necessary for providing the environmental services that humans require.

6. Growth Debate

The basic economic debate in the context of sustainability is extremely important. The issues revolves around the concept of economic growth.

1. Economic growth is desirable but feasibility need to be checked.
2. Is Economic growth is controllable?.

7. Technology and Environmental

Since the negative effects, which the public bears as social costs, are not incorporated in the private costs imposed on a market actor for production, society creates economic incentives to overstrain output. Arguments typically state that there is no quick replacement of labour with energy and capital because of technological limitations.

9. Environmental Innovation

It is difficult to deal with environmental problems with current technologies, Technological change improves environmental quality and lowering environmental pressures. Environmental technological change need to be targeted and should be close to the policy

programs and initiatives globally by Climate & Energy Framework .

10. Few Green technology innovations

Waste-water electricity generator, Artificial photosynthesis, Nuclear energy, Technology, Carbon capture and storage, Electric vehicle propulsion, Smart meters, Molten salt energy storage

11. The 3R Initiative

In order to create a society that effectively uses resources and materials, the 3Rs (reduce, reuse, and recycle) must be widely recommended (G8 Sea Island Summit in June 2004 as a new G8 programme). To formally commence, a ministerial summit was organized in Japan.

12. Renewable energy technology

Every year, renewable energy technology improves, gets more affordable, and is simpler to acquire, but it is not as widely used as might be expected. The sun, which powers our planet, produces a lot more energy than that which is necessary. In addition to these sources, there are hydropower, geothermal, biomass, and wind and solar. The green energy sector is fast changing our global energy supply systems, according to recent and disruptive advancements and inventions. The challenges are issue of surrounding efficient, affordable, and reliable energy storage. Fluctuations in sunlight levels and wind lead to less consistent than derived from fossil fuel plants. Energy storage has become less because of improved batteries at a reasonable price. Power grid supply is a important issue need to be resolved.

Energy transition pathway:

De-carbonizing the industry is one of the major issue for energy transition pathways which is not clear enough along with Govt. policies. Things are changing – fast. Our ecosystems are still being damaged by environmental and air pollution. In recent years, manufacturers have increased the size of solar photovoltaic modules and other renewable energy technologies, but there is still much work to be done. Less innovation and cost reduction. Majority still depends on fossil fuels or natural gas. Alternative fuels such as zero-carbon electricity to generate the high temperatures required, is really difficult. Collaborative approach between the public and private sectors ,resulting viable and economic solutions , which includes scale, progress, cost reduction, and scale-up in renewable energy development.

13. Concluding remarks

The best use of technology to protect environmental quality while ensuring the maximum levels of prosperity for human society and balancing human needs with environmental constraints is the requirement needed of the hour. Environmental innovation, development and deployment of Green technologies are major aspects.

Significant environmental issues are being caused by the fast industrialization, which is causing pollution of the air, water, and production of hazardous wastes. Incomplete

combustion of fuel creates huge pollution problem and needs proper attention. These aspects need to be addressed to achieve sustainable development goals. Green and sustainable technologies, which are low-carbon and beneficial to the environment, are developing rapidly.

Unfortunately, there is an obvious need to speed up the penetration of green technologies in order to develop a resilient global civilization as the detrimental environmental, health, and economic repercussions of non-sustainable decisions become ever more awful.

Worldwide interest in biofuels has increased as a result of declining petroleum reserves, a rise in energy consumption, and the unfavorable impacts of greenhouse gas emissions. Biofuels are a type of sustainable energy that effectively uses local resources while being economical, reliable, and environmentally beneficial.

It may be harmful in the long run to be extremely dependent on imported fossil fuels. The transportation industry and petroleum products are perhaps two of the industries most vulnerable to disruptions in the petroleum supply. Independently developed renewable energy is urgently needed to increase energy security and lower GDP's emission intensity.

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Dr. Subrata Mondal

Dr. Subrata Mondal passed Bachelor in Mechanical Engineering from Jalpaiguri Govt. Engineering College in 1984 and did Master Degree in Mechanical Engineering (Specialization in Heat Power) from Jadavpur University and Ph.D in Engineering from Jadavpur University. He did Master of Business Administration (Specialization in Marketing) from University of Calcutta. After around seven years of industrial experience in different Govt. of West Bengal and Govt. of India undertaking organizations at different position including erection and commissioning experience to establish a process plant. He joined as a Faculty Member at Jalpaiguri Govt. Engineering College in 1993. He has served State Administration in Technical Education of West Bengal for about 5 years. He had served Jadavpur University as Dean of Students. He had again joined at Jalpaiguri Govt. Engg. College as Professor. His expertise is on Engineering Mechanics, Thermodynamics, Heat Power etc. He has guided many thesis works in the field of Mechanical Engineering. He has visited different places in India and outside of India for academic purpose and presentation of research paper. He is the author of some Engineering books. He has also acted as an expert member of AICTE, while inspecting colleges in India. He was the Principal for Jalpaiguri Govt. Engineering College. He had also served as Principal at different Govt. Engineering Colleges in West Bengal. He had served as Technical Education Expert of Govt. of Bihar. He has given his expertise in individual capacity at different time to different industries for the national benefit. He has number of journal and conference papers. He has completed a number of project works (DST, AICTE etc.) and guided a numbers of research work for leading to Ph.D. degree. He is involved in a numbers of consultancy works.

Dr. Somnath Ghosh

Dr. Somnath Ghosh is a member of The Institution of Structural Engineers, London (MIStructE). He had served as Dean of the faculty of Engineering & Technology at Jadavpur University and had also served as country head of a division in a MNC in Nigeria, where he acted as board member. He has rendered/ rendering consultancy services to the industry for last 40 years. At present he is the Emeritus Professor of Civil Engineering, Haldia Institute of Technology (HIT) West Bengal, India. Dr. Ghosh has contributed significantly in the area of High-performance concrete, Alkali Activated composites and FEM analysis of concrete structures. He has published a huge number of papers in peer reviewed international journals and seven books through international publishing agencies. Dr. Ghosh has successfully guided a number of students for their Ph.D. and Master's Degree thesis. He has acted as expert member on several occasions for CSIR, AICTE, UGC, NAAC, NBA, IIT, IEST, NIT, WBUT & other reputed Universities. He has published a book recently on "Design of Wind and Earthquake Resistant Reinforced Concrete Buildings" by CRC press – Taylor & Francis, USA – May 2021. Dr. Ghosh has demonstrated his technical skill by providing advice on a number of occasions in solving industrial problems and the same has been implemented very successfully in practice. Served as a consultant to a number of prestigious projects at national level for NBCC, HSCL, LLOYDS INSULATION, SIKIM GOVT. PWD, AIRTEL, L&T, Airport authority, KMC, KMDA and some more.